

Notes

Chemical Investigation of the Bark and Heartwood of *Grewia asiatica* Linn.

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GREWIA *asiatica* Linn. (Tiliaceae) is an important medicinal plant and its roots, bark, leaves and fruits have been used in various ailments¹ like, rheumatism, stomachic etc. In view of these important properties and the fact that almost no work has been done so far on this plant, a chemical investigation of the plant has been undertaken in this laboratory. Preliminary studies on some sister species, *G. populifolia* Vahl²⁻³ and *G. tiliifolia* Vahl⁴ have, however, been reported.

The dried and powdered bark of the plant (2 kg) was extracted with benzene for 36 hrs. The benzene extract (15 g) was chromatographed over alumina. Elution with petroleum ether (60°–80°) yielded a product, which on crystallization (methanol), gave a colourless product A (250mg) m.p. 198°–200°. It gave positive Libermann-Burchard test and Noller's test and appeared to be a triterpene. It was identified as β -amyrin by m.m.p. determination, co-TLC and co-IR with an authentic specimen of the compound.

Further elution with petroleum-ether : benzene (4 : 1) and crystallization from methanol gave shining white flakes of product B (150 mg) m.p. 136°–7°. It gave positive Libermann-Burchard test, a yellow colour with tetranitromethane and was identified as β -sitosterol by m.m.p. determination ; co-TLC with an authentic specimen of the compound, and preparation of its acetate m.p. 128° and benzoate m.p. 144°–6°.

Elution with benzene yielded a product which on crystallization (methanol) gave a solid C (250 mg) m.p. 251°–2°. It gave positive Libermann-Burchard test and Noller's test and appeared to be a triterpene. It was identified as betulin by m.m.p. determination, co-TLC and co-IR with an authentic specimen of the compound and preparation of its diacetate m.p. 215°–1° and dibenzoate m.p. 180°.

Powdered heartwood (4 kg) of the plant was extracted with petroleum ether (60°–80°) for 40 hrs. The petroleum ether extract (10 gm) was chromatographed over alumina. Elution with petroleum ether : benzene (1 : 1) yielded a product which was identified as β -sitosterol.

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Stability of Solid Chloramin-T Towards X- and Gamma Radiation

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CHLORAMINE-T (CAT), the sodium salt of *N*-chloro *p*-toluene sulphonamide has found extensive use as an analytical reagent. Speculations about its use as a primary standard have led to controversial reports regarding its stability to heat and light¹. In the present communication, the authors have examined the stability of the solid CAT and anhydrous CAT towards ionizing radiations (X – and Co⁶⁰ gamma rays) and some preliminary results have been reported.

The experimental procedure has been described elsewhere². X-irradiations were done with 30 KVP Cu-K α radiation in an X-ray machine supplied by Radon House, Calcutta, India.

The extent of decomposition in the compounds was determined by comparison of the iodometric titer of the sample exposed to radiation with that of an unexposed sample. The percentage decomposition of the compounds was found to increase more or less linearly with the increase in absorbed dose. $G_{(-CAT)}$ values (number of molecules decomposing per 100 ev of radiant energy absorbed) are given in Table 1. A slight dose rate dependence is observed in the case of gamma irradiated CAT.

TABLE 1—GAMMA AND X-IRRADIATION OF CHLORAMINE-T AND ANHYDROUS CHLORAMINE-T.
DOSE RATES ARE GIVEN IN RADS/MIN AND ABSORBED DOSE IN EV/GM $\times 10^{19}$.

Compound	CAT (Gamma irradiation)		CAT (X-irradiation)		Anhydrous CAT (Gamma irradiation)		Anhydrous CAT (X-irradiation)			
	870		10,660		256		603			
Dose rate No.	Absorbed dose	G _{-CAT}	Absorbed dose	G _{-CAT}	Absorbed dose	G _{-CAT}	Absorbed dose	G _{-CAT}	Absorbed dose	G _{-CAT}
1	9.18	286.0	5.95	216.0	2.88	246.0	9.04	114.0	2.63	527.0
2	18.36	370.7	12.52	186.3	5.76	246.0	18.08	80.0	5.10	826.0
3	24.48	373.3	19.40	206.0	11.52	830.7	48.20	71.0	6.77	820.0
4	48.96	309.4	36.56	223.4	17.28	977.0	60.26	80.0	—	—
5	61.20	262.3	56.34	196.2	—	—	72.30	129.0	—	—
6	73.44	286.4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

The high G-values observed for the solids (Table 1) indicate that there is a chain mechanism operative in the radiation decomposition of CAT. Probably, the only other well known example of compounds showing a similar behaviour is the gamma decomposition of solid choline chloride and choline bromide³⁻⁵, with G values of the order of 10⁴. A chain mechanism has been assumed in these cases and e.s.r. studies⁴ have identified the biradical which interacts with the substrate to produce the free radical precursor for initiating the chain reaction. In gamma irradiated CAT, e.s.r. studies³ have revealed the presence of a free radical in which the odd electron is moving in a delocalized π orbital. However, a mechanism of decomposition of solid CAT can be worked out after a complete analysis of the radiolytic products.

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Study in Chelates of Some 3d Transition Elements and *p*-Dimethyl Aminoanil of 4-Hydroxyl 1-Naphthyl Glyoxyl

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GOOD amount of work¹⁻⁸ has been done on the transition metal chelates of anils from *p*-dimethylaminoaniline and nonsubstituted glyoxals (aliphatic and aromatic). In the present communication attempt is being made to study the chelates of *p*-dimethylaminoanil of 4-hydroxyl 1-naphthyl glyoxal (*), in extension.

Ligand (L), *p*-dimethylaminoanil of 4-hydroxyl 1-naphthyl glyoxal explores possibility of chelation at hydroxyl, carbonyl and azomethine groups. Most probably hydroxyl group is not participating in complexation as it is at a remotor position than that of carbonyl and azomethine adjacent groups. This paper deals with the stoichiometry and the electrolytic nature of the complexes.

Experimental

Preparation of ligand : Alcoholic solutions of 4-hydroxy 1-acetyl naphthalene⁷ (15%, w/v) and selenium

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